

Many researchers only realize after publication that they have unintentionally published in an illegitimate journal, commonly referred to as a *predatory journal*.

Publishing in a predatory journal does not automatically mean the end of your academic career. What matters now is a thoughtful, transparent, and strategic response. This guide provides practical recommendations on what to do next.

1

Stay Calm and Assess the Situation

First, carefully review the facts of your case. In particular, consider the following questions:

- Is it clearly a predatory journal?
- Have you signed a publishing agreement?
- Have you paid any Article Processing Charges (APCs)?
- Has the article already been published online?

2

Take Action Depending on the Publication Status

A) After Submission but *Before* Acceptance

If you begin to doubt the journal's legitimacy shortly after submission:

- Do not pay any Article Processing Charges (APCs) or other fees
- Do not sign any contracts or publishing agreements
- Do not agree to any additional publication terms
- Withdraw the manuscript in writing

B) *After* Manuscript Acceptance

If your manuscript has already been accepted:

- Refuse to sign any publishing agreement
- Request withdrawal of the manuscript in writing before publication
- Keep copies of all emails and documents
- Document all communication as thoroughly as possible

C) *After* Online Publication

If the article has already been published online:

- Request a retraction in writing
- Do not pay any so-called "withdrawal fees"
- Save all correspondence, invoices, and agreements
- Document the publication status (e.g., screenshots or PDF copies)

3

Seek Advice and Support

You do not have to deal with this situation on your own. Consider contacting:

- your institution's library,
- your institution's Open Access or scholarly publishing support services,
- your institution's legal department or legal counsel, if appropriate.

4

Transparency and Potential Revised Publication

Transparency

Think carefully about how you wish to address the publication in future job applications, CVs, promotion procedures, or grant applications.

In most cases, transparency is viewed more positively than attempting to conceal the issue. Consider:

- clearly indicating that the publication is problematic or has been retracted,
- briefly explaining the circumstances,
- making it clear that the publication was unintentional.

Possibility of a Revised Publication

Under certain circumstances, a substantially revised version of the article may be submitted to a legitimate journal.

To do so:

- significantly revise and expand the manuscript,
- transparently disclose the previous problematic publication,
- make it clear that the new manuscript represents a distinct and substantially revised version of the work.

5

Learn from the Experience

Use this experience to systematically reduce future publication risks.

In particular, consider:

- establishing journal evaluation procedures before every submission,
- consistently using journal assessment checklists and discovery tools,
- discussing publication practices with colleagues and early-career researchers,
- raising awareness within your institution and research community.

A structured journal evaluation process before submission is one of the most effective ways to avoid future problems.

Useful Journal Evaluation Tools

When selecting a journal, make use of established resources such as:

- [Directory of Open Access Journals \(https://doaj.org/\)](https://doaj.org/)
- [Think.Check.Submit \(https://thinkchecksubmit.org/\)](https://thinkchecksubmit.org/)
- [B!SON – Recommendation Service for Open Access Journals \(https://service.tib.eu/bison/\)](https://service.tib.eu/bison/)

For a more in-depth introduction to the topic, you may also wish to explore the accompanying self-paced online courses:

- [Predatory Journals: Identify, Avoid, and Publish Safely](#) (English version)
- [Predatory Journals erkennen und vermeiden. Sicher publizieren in der Wissenschaft](#) (German version)

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